

**FOOD COURT APPLICATION FOR TERTIARY
STUDENTS**

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STUDENTS**

by

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CERTIFICATION

I hereby declare that this project work ("Food court application for tertiary students ") is the result of my original piece of research work conducted between January/2023 and October/2023 under the supervision of Mr. Seidu Abdullah of the department of science, Al-Azhariya senior high school. In instances where references of other works have been cited, full acknowledgment has been given. This work has never been submitted in whole or in part in any institution for any award(s)

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ABSTRACT

The increasing penetration of technology in our student's lives and the advent of leisure computing among students of AU creates a fertile environment for successful thriving of an online based food ordering system. AU Food Court is an application designed primarily for use among Amity University Students. The system will allow food vendors to showcase their daily menu, which will enable users to quickly and easily scan through an online menu which they can use to place orders with just a few clicks. The respective administrators of each food vendor on the platform can then use these orders through an easy to navigate graphical user interface for efficient processing. The application provides convenience for the users. The online food ordering app sets up menus online and the customers easily place the order with a simple click. Also, with a food menu online you can easily track the orders, maintain the customer's database and improve the food delivery service. This system allows the user to select the desired food items from the displayed menu. The user orders the food items. The user's data is maintained with confidentiality as the system has a separate account for each user. An id and password are provided for each user. Therefore, it provides a more secure ordering.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Overview

In today's fast-paced world, many food vendors have chosen to concentrate on quick preparation and delivery of orders rather than offering quality service. Hitherto, all of these delivery orders were placed over the telephone but this came with it numerous disadvantages such as a customer must have a hard copy of the restaurant's menu in order to pick their choice and place the order and the menu of the restaurant must be updated regularly. This causes some form of inconvenience, again, the orders are placed using strictly oral communication which makes it more difficult for the customer to receive immediate feedback on the order they have placed and thus leading to confusion and mostly incorrect orders. On the side of the restaurant, they must have a dedicated staff to receive and return calls adding extra cost to the already choked expenses. I propose an online multi-vendor restaurant to be used among and used by AU students.

The project is a mobile-based application that helps students choose and order food from nearby restaurants. This type of mobile application is to help management keep track of what customers are ordering with ease. The app works by giving the students the option to select a restaurant of his or her choice and browse through the menu before proceeding to order. This will help users discover new restaurants, have a larger choice of menus, and save time by ordering online. The application should also give restaurant administrators a platform for processing incoming orders, as well as a way of communicating with their customers. Every new order should appear in the manager's dashboard. Managers should be able to modify their menus, publish a description for their restaurant, and upload pictures. The project will be accessible on mobile devices running on at least android API 21.

1.2 MOTIVATION

This project was motivated by the need to have a system where students can have the freedom to make choices among a list of available dishes with their respective prices from

different restaurants. A system where students can have broader consultation before arriving on their choice of dish at any point in time and not be coerced into opting in for a dish simply because they have no option available.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Healthy meal is essential to all individuals, but students of AU are presented with a limited set of options to choose from when it comes to accessing fast food from a mini-restaurant.

The few available ones have repeated choices of meal on their menu thus students are presented with different dishes to choose from. In addition, most of the few mini restaurants available tend to have cut-throat prices and do not offer competitive prices thus presenting students with no choice than to opt in for them.

1.4 Aim

To develop a system that offers streamlined operations because everything is under one dashboard and, it makes things easier for management to manage incoming orders and prepare dishes in a timely fashion. In addition, students will be presented with a system where they are able to view a variety of dishes from which they can choose from and not be subject to eating almost the same meal day-in-day-out. Finally, to have a system where shop owners can have full control of customer support which is crucial to building a loyal set of customers.

1.5 OBJECTIVE

1. To develop a system where students can order food with ease
2. To develop a system where students can have the option to read from different menus from different restaurant before making informed choice
3. To develop a system where, students can opt-in for the choice of food they can afford
4. To avoid misuse errors such as the waiter lost his order paper or the waiter's handwriting is hard to understand.

1.6 PROJECT ORGANIZATION

This chapter contains the introduction, motivation, problem statement, aims, objectives, and expected outcome. In the next chapter (2), the literature review is covered. After which, an explanation is made concerning the system architecture, as well as the flow diagram in the chapter 3 and following chapter 3 is chapter 4, where implementation tools were stated and tests are carried out on the system. Finally, chapter 5 which contains the summary, system limitations, future scope, conclusion and recommendation.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Existing System Review

2.1.1 Restaurant Point of Sale (POS)

Restaurant Point of Sale (POS) have been providing a bar and restaurant system which is called jRestaurant POS. That restaurant system is ideal for all catering environments being a pizzeria, a fast-food, fine dining, a cafeteria or any other food-service. The restaurant system can be installed on any computer running Microsoft Windows. Apart from the desktop version which is installed on a normal PC, users can add a wireless interface to their POS restaurant system. Users can purchase the PDA plug-in which is installed on a wireless PDA.

Figure 2.1: Restaurant POS

That restaurant system allows multiple transactions to occur at the same time and prevents any human errors which are quite normal especially in high season.

2.1.2 Multi-Touchable E-Restaurant Management System Multi-touch technology is an enhancement to the existing touch technology whereby users are allowed to control and perform operations simultaneously on the electronic visual displays using multiple fingers or gesture

inputs. Large displays such as from the table top and the wall-screen are deemed to be essentials when dealing with multiple users sharing the same display for information visualization purposes. It is reported that social interaction is highly improved among users using a shared display and input.

According to Cheong, Chiew & Yap (2010), one of the technologies that have been adopted by restaurants is the PDA-based wireless food ordering system. Various applications have been developed specially for such a restaurant ordering system, which include iMenu, a web-based ordering system that runs on wireless connection and Easy-Order, the first application developed to communicate with computers to deliver e-commerce tasks.

Businesses that implemented such mobile technologies generally improved their operation efficiency, reduced operating costs, and improved service quality. Another important aspect of the restaurant ordering system is the dining menu. Dining menu ought to be informative, attractive and updated all the time for customers to make orders easily. Restaurant owners strive to outwit each other by introducing new promotions, new food menus and new attractive announcements. By doing so, the dining menu is frequently changed, which involves huge amounts of money and time. The multi-touchable dining menu on the dining table provides the interface for customers to order food at their table. The menu serves as an informational platform that allows users to browse and view food details, an ordering platform that gives customers place and manage orders digitally on top of the dining table.

Multi-touchable E-restaurant management system solved some of the limitations encountered by the PDA-based food ordering system.

Figure 2.2: User Interface of Multi-touch technology

2.1.3 A Personalized Restaurant Recommender Agent for Mobile E-Service

A recommender agent in mobile environments should be context-aware to assist users while the users are moving. Many different kinds of contexts can be used by a recommender agent, such as weather, route conditions, time and location, etc.

Tung & Soo (2004) identify that PDA is chosen as the hardware for implementing the agents, the Personal Handyphone System (PHS) as the wireless connection of the PDA, and the Global Positioning System (GPS) for the agent to determine the current position of the user. There are two types of agents in that system, first is the context-aware personalized agent (CAPA) and second is the restaurant directory service agent (RDSA). The CAPA resides in the PDA of the user (Figure 2.6). The main role in the multi-agent system is to interact with the user and the RDSA. CAPA is capable of getting user's preferences for selecting restaurants. For the mobile user, CAPA can explore the user's time and spatial context by the built-in sensor capabilities. To use that system, a new restaurant must register in the restaurant directory with RDSA before it can be recommended to the user. The entry will contain information about the restaurant. The RDSA also has the ability to search restaurants given preference constraints. If the RDSA couldn't find anything according to these preference constraints, it will propose some modifications to the constraints. It also has the ability of recommending a restaurant out of many matched ones.

2.1.4 Comparison between all the existing systems.

The table shows a comparison operating system between all the existing systems consulted.

Feature	Manual System	Restaurant Point of Sale (POS)	Multi-Touchable E-Restaurant Management System	Personalized Restaurant Recommender Agent for Mobile E-Service
Hardware	Pen, Paper, File	Computer, Mobile(PDA)	Computer, Mobile(PDA)	Computer, GPS, Mobile(PDA)
Software	Not available	Visual Basic	PHP	PHP
Language	Not available	VB.net	XML	HTML
Setting	Not available	Easy to setting	Hard to setting	Hard to setting
Methods	Not available	SDLC	SDLC	SDLC
Accessible via Internet	Not accessible	Accessible through Internet, must use WIFI for communication.	Accessible through Internet, must use WIFI for communication.	Accessible through Internet, must use WIFI for communication.
Management system	Manual management system is being record manually by pen and books	The POS management system is based on the computerized system.	The Multi-Touchable E-Restaurant management system is based on the computerized system.	The Personalized Restaurant Recommender Agent for Mobile E-Service management system is based on the computerized system.

Figure 2.3: Comparison between all the existing systems.

2.2 RECENT TRENDS

1. Food Delivery Subscription

The trend of delivery subscriptions has found a perfect match in both specialized online food delivery and the millennial generation. Roughly speaking, people born between the early 1980's and mid-2000's are the largest age demographic in the U.S. and are driving massive changes in the food delivery industry. Millennials are the first generation that would rather stay in than go out, and that often translates to dining in with a customized meal kit delivered to their door. Pre-prepared fresh meals, menu kits with raw ingredients, and other home food kits that save customers time are top draws for the 55% of millennials that prioritize convenience over even taste, according to the Food Information Council. These subscription boxes also cater to consumers interested in trying new or different cuisines, something that the booming food market has enabled. Add to this the rising number of consumers looking for vegan, organic, no-gluten, paleo or ethically-sourced food, and you'll understand the continued growth of specialized food subscriptions. With online orders growing at a faster pace than ever, food operators have an unprecedented opportunity to increase profit margins and customer reach. The challenge will be to balance the customer demand for fast, convenient and transparent delivery with the logistical complexity and expenses required to meet these demands.

2. Tech Giants Moving in on Food Delivery

Back in 2017, Amazon made waves when it acquired Whole Foods in an attempt to take on the grocery market. Then Uber Eats came in with a platform for grocery and restaurant delivery. Google began to enable food ordering and delivery directly from Search and Maps. Partner restaurants will have orders integrated into the search and map functions, enabling people to order directly from the search results page. Deliveries will be fulfilled by the same fleets currently used by the restaurants. Now that a great percent of revenue for food businesses is invested in online sales and off-premise fulfilment like delivery, curb side pickup and drive-thru, we expect this trend will only grow as tech giants step in with investments, marketplaces, and new services.

3. Tracking Delivery Data

With such a large part of the delivery flow in the hands of third parties, it's not surprising food providers are turning to data collection and analysis to better understand their delivery operations. In April 2019, McDonalds spent \$300 million to acquire a big data startup. The multi-billion-dollar conglomerate understood that the best way to stay ahead of the competition is to measure, analyse, and improve your performance. Having these insights into your own delivery operations is invaluable and the benefits stretch across everything from relations with external fleets and aggregators, to providing flawless deliveries, to enabling other arms of your business, like customer care, marketing and branding.

4. In-House Restaurant Delivery Fleets

Some companies are taking a completely different approach to the one described above by doing something fairly radical: building in-house delivery fleets. Panera launched its in-house delivery operation back in 2016, bucking the trend at the time. Today, it's one of the few restaurant chains that doesn't hand over a large chunk of its delivery revenue to third party providers. Today companies like Chick-fil-A are exploring in-house delivery and the great benefits it offers such as full visibility and control over customer data and branding. To smoothly manage these operations in-house, restaurants need delivery dispatch software, which uses automation to assign drivers to each order. When delivery happens at scale, with tens of thousands of orders each day (or more), the logistics behind it become increasingly complex, which is why chains managing delivery across multiple restaurants get the most value out of using delivery management software systems.

2.3 PROBLEMS AND SHORTCOMINGS OF THEIR WORK

The striking shortfall across all the literature reviewed in this project is that none of the systems they use is flexible enough to allow customers to order food from their respective locations. The system employed so far all made use of desktop based software and thus one has to be present in the restaurant to use the system.

2.4 BRIDGING THE GAP

The purpose of the project and its intended purpose is to create a system where students, from the comfort of their homes or hostel can read the menu of the available restaurant on the mobile, application, place an order and have it delivered to them whiles being presented with the power to make a choice from a competitive list of food vendors on the app.

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

There are multi-vendor food ordering apps such as hubtel. These apps are for general purpose food ordering and not tailored to only Amity University Students (AU), hence the focus is not entirely on AU students. Also, these platforms have a huge amount of people ordering food and many conflicting interests which increases the probability of being presented with many options generating a state of confusion. Existing platforms such as hubtel charge a platform fee of 1% of total, and payment processing fee. This leads to a deduction from the total amount paid by the students. This charge increases the amount of money the student has to pay to purchase his or her dish.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system, which is referred to as AU Food app, is developed to enable students to easily order food from food vendors closest to campus quickly and easily. AU Food Court is focused primarily on food ordering by AU Students hence there is no space for those food vendors outside the University campus. Students who order food are assured of getting food from vendors whom they know and can trust hence they are getting healthy meals from trusted sources. This helps to drastically reduce the number of junk food that the student will feast on. AU Food app does not take a percentage on food orders, it only charges 1.9% which helps to cover the processing fees.

3.3 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

AU Food app is a system that is made up of a web interface, a mobile app, and a backend. The web interface is designed primarily to enable administrators' approve or reject a request by food vendors. The web interface also has a landing page which contains a link to download the mobile app and informs visitors about the purpose of the application. The mobile app allows the students to quickly register on the system, order food and track the status of their order. The backend is the core of the system which is responsible for authentication and authorization of users, persisting of data, performing CRUD (Create, Read, Update and Delete) operations, and executing business logic. The backend also has an API (Application Programming Interface) that enables the mobile application to communicate seamlessly with the backend. For this project, I chose the agile software development methodology to enable me to focus on delivering a minimum viable product (MVP). A broad overview of the structure of the system is show below:

Fig. 3.1 Overall Architecture

The figure (fig. 3.1) above shows the architecture of the system. A food vendor uses the mobile app to place a request for food selling space, the application is sent by the API to the backend where it is stored in the database. The administrator then uses the web interface to review the application retrieved from the database.

3.3.1 BACK-END

The backend is written in a scripting language called PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor). PHP is a popular general-purpose scripting language that is especially suited to web development. To ensure that I can focus on building the core features of the projects rather than reinventing the wheel, I used a PHP framework called Laravel which enabled me to boost the performance and efficiency of developing the application. Laravel is a web application framework with expressive and elegant syntax which lays down the foundation – freeing you to create applications without sweating the small things. Laravel uses the Model - View – Controller (MVC) architecture, The Model-View-Controller (MVC) is an architectural pattern that separates an application into three main logical components: the model, the view, and the controller.

The backend is made up of a lot of files and folders, the most critical ones are: index.php, web.php, api.php, controllers, models, views, and migrations. Index.php is the starting point of the backend application, it is responsible for running the application. The web.php contains the various URLs that can be used to navigate around the application in the browser. The api.php on the other hand contains the API endpoints that will be called by the mobile application. The

controllers' folder contains the controllers. Controllers act as an interface between Model and View components to process all the business logic and incoming requests, manipulate data using the Model component and interact with the Views to render the final output. The models' folder contains the classes that provide an interface to interacting with the application data. There are four models that are used at the backend:

1. Application Model:

The application model is an eloquent model that can be used to query, or modify the applications tables. The application model also defines the relationship between a category, user and an application. The application model also contains three business logic functions which are responsible for changing a vendor's status to approved, rejected, and pending.

2. Category Model:

The category model is also an eloquent model that enables the backend query or manipulates the category table using an expressive syntax. The category model also defines a one-to-many relationship between the category table and the applications table.

3. Feedback Model:

The feedback model is an eloquent model that enables the application to interact with the feedback table. The feedbacks are issues, or suggestions that are provided by the user to ensure that the project is meeting the user's needs.

4. User Model:

The user model is an eloquent model that enables the application to interact with the users table. With the help of the user model, the backend is able to authenticate, authorize, create and delete users on the system. The user model also defines a one-to-many relationship between the user and applications table. The one-to-many relationship ensures that a user can have more than one application. The views folder contains all the UI logic of the application. The view folder contains the blade files that enables us to write PHP and HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) together in a clean way. The views folder contains the implementation of pages such as the login, signup, landing page, and admin dashboard. The migrations folder contains files that enable the creation and manipulation of tables. A migration allows the programmer to create a table in the database without actually going to the database manager such as phpMyAdmin.

3.3.2 FRONT-END

The front-end consists of two main sections: the landing page and the admin dashboard. The landing page provides information about what the application is about and a download button for downloading the mobile app. The admin dashboard enables administrators to review applications. The admin dashboard is only accessible by authorized users.

The front-end consists of the following pages:

1. Homepage
2. Login Page
3. Administrator Dashboard
4. Application Details Page
5. Comments Page
6. Forgot Password Page

3.3.3 MOBILE APP

The mobile app was implemented using the flutter framework. Flutter is Google's UI (User Interface) toolkit for building beautiful, natively compiled applications for mobile, web, and desktop from a single codebase. The mobile app code is organized into six various sections namely: components, controllers, models, screens, services and utils. The components are UI elements that are shared between several components such as buttons, and progress

indicators. The controllers contain business-logic, the models are classes which define the structure of the data used in the app. The services folder contains the functions that make API calls to the backend, retrieve data and present it to the controllers. The utils folder contains functions and configurations that are shared between various components of the application.

The screens folder contains the various screens/pages that the user can navigate to in the mobile app. The screens available in the mobile application are:

1. Splash Screen
2. Onboarding Screen
3. Login Screen
4. Register Screen
5. Forgot Password Screen
6. Home Screen
7. All Vendors Screen
8. Individual Vendor Details Screen

9. Cart Screen
10. Order Screen
11. History Screen
12. Feedback Screen

3.4 USE CASE

The system comprises three main actors namely: Admin, Vendor, and Users. These three actors have different privileges in the system, which are the various functionalities they have access to.

3.4.1 USER:

The applicant is the actor that mostly interacts with the mobile application. The primary actions performed by the user are presented. The applicant should be able to place an order, view and track the order, edit the order or delete the order when it is no longer needed.

3.4.2 VENDOR:

The vendor can also interact with the mobile application but this interaction is limited to viewing a list of his or her orders on the home screen, and sending feedback. The other actions that can be performed by the donor are presented.

3.4.3 ADMIN:

The role of the admin is important to manage the various applications received from the mobile application. The admin use case in figure 3.4 displays all the potential actions that the admin can perform. The admin user makes the decision of either accepting or rejecting a vendor's request. The admin also has the ability to view the feedback sent by the different users.

3.5 CONCLUSION

This chapter explained the overall architecture of the system focusing on the main modules and how they work. The use cases diagram highlighted the overview of the application specifying various users and the privileges. The next chapter will focus on the implementation and testing which would outline how the application was implemented and the various tools used, the various kinds of test and also showing snapshots of the result of the main modules.

CHAPTER 4

IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION TOOLS

The project was developed on a laptop with a Linux operating system, specifically Ubuntu 22.04. The web application was developed with a PHP framework (Laravel), while the mobile application was developed with Flutter. Flutter is a Dart framework for developing fast and beautiful cross-platform mobile applications. The different tools used for the backend, frontend and mobile app are as follows:

WEB APPLICATION

1. HTML – Hypertext Markup Language: Defines the structure of the web page
2. CSS – Cascading Style Sheet: Used for styling the web page
3. JavaScript: An object-oriented computer programming language commonly used to provide functionality or create interactive effects within web browsers.
4. PHP: PHP is a server-side scripting language. That is used to develop Static websites or Dynamic websites or Web applications. The Laravel framework used in this project was developed using PHP.
5. Blade: Blade is the simple, yet powerful templating engine that is included with Laravel. Blade also enables you to write plain PHP code in your HTML.
6. Tailwind CSS: Tailwind is a utility-first CSS framework packed with classes that can be composed to build any design, directly in your markup.
7. Laravel: Laravel is a PHP framework that attempts to take the pain out of development by easing common tasks used in the majority of web projects, such as authentication, routing, sessions, and caching.
8. MySQL: MySQL is an open-source relational database management system which is popularly used to persist structured data in web applications. I used MySQL because it has been in development for long, and suits this application needs perfectly.

MOBILE APPLICATION

1. Dart: Dart is a client-optimized language for fast apps on any platform developed by Google.
2. Flutter: Flutter is Google’s UI (User Interface) toolkit for building beautiful, natively

compiled applications for mobile, web, and desktop from a single codebase

3. **WebView Flutter:** WebView is a flutter plugin that provides a WebView widget which enables us to visit websites directly in our mobile application.

4. **GETX:** GetX is an extra-light and powerful solution for Flutter. It combines high-performance state management, intelligent dependency injection, and route management quickly and practically.

5. **Shared Preferences:** This flutter package provides platform-specific storage for simple data.

6. **Http:** The flutter http library is a composable, Future-based library for making HTTP requests. This library contains a set of high-level functions and classes that make it easy to consume HTTP resources. It's multi-platform, and supports mobile, desktop, and the browser.

7. **Image Picker & Image Cropper:** Image Picker is a Flutter plugin for iOS and Android for picking images from the image library, and taking new pictures with the camera. The Image Cropper plugin provides the functionality to crop pictures received from the Image Picker.

4.2 DATABASE SPECIFICATION

The database system used to implement the backend of the system is called MySQL.

MySQL is an open-source relational database management system. The database consists of six main tables:

1. Vendors Table
2. Categories Table
3. Feedback Table
4. Users Table
5. Personal Access Tokens Table
6. Password Resets Table

VENDORS TABLE

Field	Type	Null	Key
id	bigint (20)	No	PRIMARY
title	varchar(255)	No	
description	text	No	
image_url	varchar (255)	No	
price	double (8,2)	No	
approved	tinyint (3)	No	
user_id	bigint (20)	No	Foreign
category_id	bigint (20)	No	Foreign
created_at	timestamp	Yes	
updated_at	Timestamp	Yes	

Table 4.1 database applications table.

CATEGORIES TABLE

Field	Type	Null	Key
id	bigint (20)	No	PRIMARY
name	varchar (255)	No	FOREIGN
created_at	timestamp	Yes	
updated_at	timestamp	Yes	

Table 4.2 database categories table.

FEEDBACK TABLE

Field	Type	Null	Key
id	bigint (20)	No	PRIMARY
comment	text	No	
rating	double (8,2)	No	
created_at	timestamp	Yes	
updated_at	timestamp	Yes	

Table 4.3 database feedback table.

USERS TABLE

Field	Type	Null	Key
index	bigint (20)	No	PRIMARY
name	varchar (255)	No	
email	varchar (255)	No	Foreign
email_verified_at	timestamp	Yes	
admin	tinyint (1)	Yes	
password	varchar (255)	No	
remember_token	varchar (100)	Yes	
created_at	timestamp	Yes	
updated_at	timestamp	Yes	

Table 4.5 database personal access tokens table.

PERSONALACCESS TOKENS TABLE

Field	Type	Null	Key
id	bigint (20)	No	PRIMARY
tokenable_type	varchar (255)	No	Foreign
tokenable_id	bigint (20)	No	Foreign
name	varchar (255)	No	
token	varchar (64)	No	Foreign
abilities	text	Yes	
last_used	timestamp	Yes	
created_at	timestamp	Yes	
updated_at	timestamp	Yes	

Table 4.5 database personal access tokens table.

PASSWORD RESETS TABLE

Field	Type	Null	Key
email	varchar (255)	No	Foreign
token	varchar (255)	No	
created_at	timestamp	Yes	

ENTITY-RELATIONSHIP DIAGRAM

The diagram below contains an entity-relationship diagram which showcases the various entities in the database, as well as their cardinalities and how they relate to one another.

ER DIAGRAM

Figure 4.1: E-R Diagram for Food Court Management System

4.3 TESTING

The mobile application and web application were tested thoroughly to ensure that the application performed well. While performing these tests bugs were discovered and eliminated to ensure that bugs encountered by users will be minimal.

4.4 SCREENSHOT OF THE SYSTEM

Login Screen: The login screen is quick and allows the user to enter his or credentials to login to the application.

Figure 4.2: Login Screen

Register Screen: the login screen is quick and allows the user to create an account on the application.

Figure 4.3: Register Screen

Welcome Screen: the welcome screen allows the user to select a vendor among a list of vendors.

Figure 4.4: Welcome Screen

Individual Vendor Screen: this screen displays the various dishes from a particular vendor.

Figure 4.5: Individual Vendor Screen

Breakfast Screen: this screen displays the various dishes from breakfast only.

Figure 4.6: Breakfast Screen

Detail Screen: this screen displays the details about a particular food dish.

Figure 4.7: Detail Screen

Checkout Screen: This is the checkout screen where a user select the means of payment

Figure 4.8: Checkout Screen

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

5.1 SUMMARY

At the end of this project, I was able to design and develop a mobile and web application that enabled students of Amity University to be able to order food online. Features such as ensuring only approved vendors were visible on the home screen made users be able to order and receive ordered food to be delivered to them. This project has the potential to make the life of students easier when it comes to accessing food. The systematic approach used during each phase of the software development provides a clear road map that would be of immense help to anyone carrying out research in this area.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The development of AU Food Court app involved many phases. The first phase started with detailed study of the problem, the problem of the existing system was documented and used as the basis for the system design, which immediately followed the first phase. The design phase was concerned primarily with the specification of the systems element in a manner that best meets the Students' needs. To ensure that we tackle one side of the application at a time. We decided to develop the mobile application first before working on the web interface that will be used by the Administrator. After implementing the core features which were registering on the platform, ordering for food from vendors and receiving the orders. I then moved to implementing the dashboard that will enable the Admin to either accept or reject the vendor's application request. It is hoped that effective implementation of this software product would reduce the number of students who feast on unhealthy meals from outside the university campus.

5.3 LIMITATION

One of the limitations of the project is the inability to allow students outside the university's premises to also place orders and have it delivered to them at their homes. In addition, mobile money payment is not possible as the project has to be registered legally before that can be approved.

5.4 FUTURE SCOPE

The future of AU Food Court app will involve allowing organizations to also register and market their dishes on the platform. To expand the solution for a larger audience, we need to enhance the payment system to reflect the funds paid to a vendor directly. Also, a service like cloudinary will help reduce the images on the server and will enable us to continue delivering images to users at an optimal speed.

For now, the application can be installed on android phones and iPhone. We plan to develop a web application to enable users that do not have access to smartphones to also apply.

APPENDICES

BACKEND CODES:

ROUTES

api.php

```
<?php
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Route;
use App\Http\Controllers\AuthController;
use App\Http\Controllers\CategoryController;
use App\Http\Controllers\ApplicationController;
use App\Http\Controllers\FeedbackController;
/*
|-----
| API Routes
|-----
|
| Here is where you can register API routes for your application. These
| routes are loaded by the RouteServiceProvider within a group which
| is assigned the "api" middleware group. Enjoy building your API!
|
*/
Route::post('/register', [AuthController::class, 'register']);
Route::post('/login', [AuthController::class, 'login']);
Route::post('/forgot-password', [AuthController::class, 'sendResetLink']);
Route::get('/categories', [CategoryController::class, 'index']);
Route::get('/applications', [ApplicationController::class, 'index']);
Route::get('/feedbacks', [FeedbackController::class, 'index']);
Route::post('/feedbacks', [FeedbackController::class, 'store']);
Route::get('/applications/{id}', [ApplicationController::class, 'show']);
Route::group(['middleware' => ['auth:sanctum']], function () {
Route::get('/user', function () {
return auth()->user();
});
Route::get('/user/applications', [ApplicationController::class, 'user']);
Route::post('/applications', [ApplicationController::class, 'store']);
Route::post('/applications/{id}', [ApplicationController::class, 'update'
]);
Route::delete('/applications/{id}', [ApplicationController::class, 'destro
y']);
});
```

web.php

```
<?php
use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Route;
use App\Notifications\ApiPasswordResetNotification;
use App\Http\Controllers\DashboardController;
/*
|-----
| Web Routes
|-----
|
```

```

| Here is where you can register web routes for your application. These
| routes are loaded by the RouteServiceProvider within a group which
| contains the "web" middleware group. Now create something great!
|
*/
Route::get('/', function () {
return view('welcome');
});
// Route::get('/mail', function () {
// return (new ApiPasswordResetNotification(43445))->toMail('www');
// });
Route::group(['middleware' => ['auth', 'verify.admin']], function () {
Route::get('/dashboard', [DashboardController::class, 'index']->name('das
hboard'));
Route::get('/dashboard/detail/{id}', [DashboardController::class, 'detail'
]);
Route::get('/dashboard/feedbacks', [DashboardController::class, 'feedbacks
']->name('feedbacks'));
Route::get('/dashboard/approve/{id}', [DashboardController::class, 'approv
e']);
Route::get('/dashboard/reject/{id}', [DashboardController::class, 'reject'
]);
Route::get('/dashboard/pending/{id}', [DashboardController::class, 'pendin
g']);
});
require __DIR__.'/auth.php';

```

CONTROLLERS

ApplicationController:

```

<?php
namespace App\Http\Controllers;
use App\Models\Application;
use App\Http\Resources\ApplicationResource;
use App\Traits\ApiResponder;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Storage;
class ApplicationController extends Controller
{
use ApiResponder;
/**
* Display a listing of the resource.
*
* @return \Illuminate\Http\Response
*/
public function index()
{
return $this->success(
ApplicationResource::collection(Application::where('approved', 1)-
>get()),
'Applications fetched successfully',
200

```

```

);
}
public function user()
{
$user_id = auth()->id();
return $this->success(
ApplicationResource::collection(Application::where('user_id', $user_id)->get()),
'Applications fetched successfully',
200
);
}
/**
 * Store a newly created resource in storage.
 *
 * @param \Illuminate\Http\Request $request
 * @return \Illuminate\Http\Response
 */
public function store(Request $request)
{
$application = new Application;
$validator = validator($request->all(), [
'title' => 'required|string',
'description' => 'required|string',
'image_url' => 'required|image:jpeg,png,jpg,gif,svg|max:5120',
'target_amount' => 'required|string',
'category_id' => 'required|numeric'
]);
if ($validator->fails()) {
return $this->error("Validation failed", 400, $validator->errors()->all());
}
$uploadFolder = 'applications';
$image = $request->file('image_url');
$image_uploaded_path = $image->store($uploadFolder, 'public');
$application->user_id = auth()->user()->id;
$application->title = $request->title;
$application->description = $request->description;
$application->image_url = $image_uploaded_path;
$application->target_amount = $request->target_amount;
$application->category_id = $request->category_id;
$application->save();
$newApplication = Application::findOrFail($application->id);
return $this->success(
new ApplicationResource($newApplication),
'Application was created successfully'
);
}
/**
 * Display the specified resource.
 *
 * @param \App\Models\Application $application

```

```

* @return \Illuminate\Http\Response
*/
public function show($id)
{
return $this->success(
new ApplicationResource(Application::findOrFail($id)),
'Application retrieved successfully',
200
);
}
/**
* Update the specified resource in storage.
*
* @param \Illuminate\Http\Request $request
* @param \App\Models\Application $application
* @return \Illuminate\Http\Response
*/
public function update(Request $request, $id)
{
$application = Application::findOrFail($id);
$validator = validator($request->all(), [
'title' => 'required|string',
'description' => 'required|string',
'image_url' => 'required|image:jpeg,png,jpg,gif,svg|max:5120',
'target_amount' => 'required|string',
'category_id' => 'required|numeric'
]);
if ($validator->fails()) {
return $this->error("Validation failed", 400, $validator->errors()
->all());
}
$this->authorize('update', $application);
$uploadFolder = 'applications';
$existing_image_path = $application->image_url;
Storage::disk('public')->delete($existing_image_path);
$new_image_path = $request->file('image_url')->store($uploadFolder, 'p
ublic');
$application->title = $request->title;
$application->description = $request->description;
$application->image_url = $new_image_path;
$application->approved = 0;
$application->target_amount = floatval($request->target_amount);
$application->category_id = $request->category_id;
$application->save();
return $this->success(
new ApplicationResource($application),
'Application updated successfully'
);
}
/**
* Remove the specified resource from storage.
*

```

```

* @param \App\Models\Application $application
* @return \Illuminate\Http\Response
*/
public function destroy($id)
{
    $application = Application::findOrFail($id);
    $this->authorize('delete', $application);
    Storage::disk('public')->delete($application->image_url);
    if($application->delete()){
        return $this->success(
            'Application deleted successfully'
        );
    }
}
}
}

```

Migrations

create_users_table

```

<?php
use Illuminate\Database\Migrations\Migration;
use Illuminate\Database\Schema\Blueprint;
use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Schema;
class CreateUsersTable extends Migration
{
    /**
     * Run the migrations.
     *
     * @return void
     */
    public function up()
    {
        Schema::create('users', function (Blueprint $table) {
            $table->id();
            $table->string('name');
            $table->string('email')->unique();
            $table->timestamp('email_verified_at')->nullable();
            $table->boolean('admin')->nullable();
            $table->string('password');
            $table->rememberToken();
            $table->timestamps();
        });
    }
    /**
     * Reverse the migrations.
     *
     * @return void
     */
    public function down()
    {
        Schema::dropIfExists('users');
    }
}

```

create_categories_table

```

<?php
use Illuminate\Database\Migrations\Migration;
use Illuminate\Database\Schema\Blueprint;
use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Schema;
class CreateCategoriesTable extends Migration
{
/**
 * Run the migrations.
 *
 * @return void
 */
public function up()
{
Schema::create('categories', function (Blueprint $table) {
$table->id();
$table->string('name')->unique();
$table->timestamps();
});
}
/**
 * Reverse the migrations.
 *
 * @return void
 */
public function down()
{
Schema::dropIfExists('categories');
}
}
create_applications_table
<?php
use Illuminate\Database\Migrations\Migration;
use Illuminate\Database\Schema\Blueprint;
use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Schema;
class CreateApplicationsTable extends Migration
{
/**
 * Run the migrations.
 *
 * @return void
 */
public function up()
{
Schema::create('applications', function (Blueprint $table) {
$table->id();
$table->string('title');
$table->text('description');
$table->string('image_url');
$table->float('target_amount');
$table->float('amount_gained')->default(0);
$table->unsignedTinyInteger('approved')->default(0);
$table->unsignedBigInteger('user_id');

```

```

$table->foreign('user_id')->references('id')->on('users');
$table->unsignedBigInteger('category_id');
$table->foreign('category_id')->references('id')->on('categories')
;
$table->timestamps();
});
}
/**
 * Reverse the migrations.
 *
 * @return void
 */
public function down()
{
Schema::dropIfExists('applications');
}
}
create_feedback_table
<?php
use Illuminate\Database\Migrations\Migration;
use Illuminate\Database\Schema\Blueprint;
use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Schema;
class CreateFeedbackTable extends Migration
{
/**
 * Run the migrations.
 *
 * @return void
 */
public function up()
{
Schema::create('feedback', function (Blueprint $table) {
$table->id();
$table->text('comment');
$table->float('rating');
$table->timestamps();
});
}
/**
 * Reverse the migrations.
 *
 * @return void
 */
public function down()
{
Schema::dropIfExists('feedback');
}
}
MOBILE APP CODES:
main.dart
import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
import 'package:get/get.dart';

```

```

import 'package:mobileapp/screens/home/home.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/screens/onboarding/onboarding_screen.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/utils/themeconfigurations.dart';
import 'package:shared_preferences/shared_preferences.dart';
int initScreen;
Future<void> main() async {
WidgetsFlutterBinding.ensureInitialized();
SharedPreferences preferences = await SharedPreferences.getInstance();
initScreen = preferences.getInt("initScreen");
await preferences.setInt("initScreen", 1);
runApp(MyApp());
}
class MyApp extends StatelessWidget {
@override
Widget build(BuildContext context) {
return GetMaterialApp(
debugShowCheckedModeBanner: false,
title: 'EDU FUND',
theme: themeConfigurations(),
initialRoute: initScreen == 0 || initScreen == null ? "first" : "/",
routes: {
'/': (context) => HomeScreen(),
"first": (context) => OnboardingScreen(),
},
);
}
}

```

SCREENS

application_list.dart

```

import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
import 'package:flutter_spinkit/flutter_spinkit.dart';
import 'package:flutter_svg/flutter_svg.dart';
import 'package:get/get.dart';
import 'package:get/instance_manager.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/controllers/application_controller.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/screens/applications/components/application_card.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/utils/contants.dart';
class ApplicationList extends StatelessWidget {
final ApplicationController applicationController =
Get.put(ApplicationController());
@override
Widget build(BuildContext context) {
return Expanded(
child: Obx(() {
if (applicationController.isLoading.value) {
return Center(
child: SpinKitPumpingHeart(
color: Colors.green,
size: 100,
),
);
}
});
}

```

```

} else if (applicationController.errorOccurred.value) {
return Center(
child: Column(
mainAxisAlignment: MainAxisAlignment.center,
children: [
SvgPicture.asset(
"assets/icons/nointernet.svg",
width: MediaQuery.of(context).size.width,
),
SizedBox(
height: 30,
),
Text(
applicationController.errorMessage.value.capitalize,
textAlign: TextAlign.center,
style: TextStyle(
fontWeight: FontWeight.bold,
fontSize: 24,
color: Colors.grey[800],
),
),
SizedBox(
height: 30,
),
FlatButton(
onPressed: applicationController.fetchApplications,
color: kPrimaryColor,
height: 50.0,
minWidth: MediaQuery.of(context).size.width * 0.4,
shape: RoundedRectangleBorder(
borderRadius: BorderRadius.circular(25.0),
),
child: Text(
"Retry",
style: TextStyle(
color: Colors.white, fontWeight: FontWeight.bold),
),
),
],
),
);
}
return RefreshIndicator(
onRefresh: applicationController.fetchApplications,
child: ListView.builder(
itemCount: applicationController.applicationList.length,
itemBuilder: (BuildContext context, int index) {
return Column(children: [
ApplicationCard(
application: applicationController.applicationList[index],
)
]);
});

```

```

},
),
);
}),
);
}
}

```

application_detail.dart

```

import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
import 'package:get/get.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/components/application_description.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/components/default_button.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/components/linearprogressindicator.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/models/application.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/utils/constants.dart';
import 'package:url_launcher/url_launcher.dart';
import 'package:flutter/services.dart';

class ApplicationDetailScreen extends StatelessWidget {
  final Application application;
  const ApplicationDetailScreen({Key key, this.application}) : super(key: key)
  ;
  @override
  Widget build(BuildContext context) {
    return Scaffold(
      appBar: AppBar(
        title: Text('Details'),
        elevation: 3,
      ),
      bottomNavigationBar: BottomAppBar(
        child: Padding(
          padding: EdgeInsets.symmetric(vertical: 15, horizontal: 10),
          child: DefaultButton(
            text: "Fund this student".toUpperCase(),
            press: () {
              // Get.to(PaymentPage());
              launch('https://paystack.com/pay/edufund');
            },
          ),
        ),
      ),
      body: SingleChildScrollView(
        child: Padding(
          padding: EdgeInsets.all(8.0),
          child: Container(
            child: Column(
              children: [
                Image.network(
                  application.imageUrl,
                  fit: BoxFit.cover,
                  width: MediaQuery.of(context).size.width,
                  height: MediaQuery.of(context).size.height * 0.25,
                ),
              ],
            ),
          ),
        ),
      ),
    );
  }
}

```



```

Padding(
padding: EdgeInsets.only(bottom: 6),
child: Text(
(application.progress * 100).toInt().toString()
+
'%',
style: TextStyle(
color: Colors.blue,
fontSize: 15,
),
),
),
),
),
Padding(
padding: EdgeInsets.only(bottom: 6),
child: Text(
'GHS ' + application.targetAmount.toString(),
style: TextStyle(
color: Colors.blue,
fontSize: 15,
),
),
),
),
),
],
),
),
),
),
),
),
),
),
),
),
),
),
),
);
}
}

```

SERVICES

application_services.dart

```

import 'dart:convert' as convert;
import 'package:get/get.dart';
import 'package:http/http.dart' as http;
import 'package:mobileapp/models/application.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/models/editApplication.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/models/newApplication.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/utills/endpoints.dart';
import 'package:mobileapp/utills/user_preferences.dart';

```

```

class ApplicationServices extends GetConnect {
static var client = http.Client();
static Future<List<Application>> fetchApplications() async {
var response = await client.get(AppUrl.applications);
if (response.statusCode == 200) {
var jsonResponse = convert.jsonDecode(response.body);
var applications = jsonResponse['data'];
return applicationFromJson(convert.jsonEncode(applications));
} else {
return null;
}
}
static Future<List<Application>> fetchUserApplications() async {
final UserPreferences userPreferences = Get.put(UserPreferences());
userPreferences.getUser();
var userToken = userPreferences.user.value.token;
var response = await client.get(
AppUrl.userApplications,
headers: {
'Accept': 'application/json',
'Authorization': 'Bearer ' + userToken,
},
);
if (response.statusCode == 200) {
var jsonResponse = convert.jsonDecode(response.body);
var applications = jsonResponse['data'];
return applicationFromJson(convert.jsonEncode(applications));
} else {
return null;
}
}
Future<Application> newApplication(NewApplication newApplicationData) async
{
final UserPreferences userPreferences = Get.put(UserPreferences());
userPreferences.getUser();
var userToken = userPreferences.user.value.token;
final form = FormData({
'title': newApplicationData.title,
'description': newApplicationData.description,
'image_url':
MultipartFile(newApplicationData.imageUrl, filename: 'new.jpg'),
'target_amount': newApplicationData.targetAmount,
'category_id': newApplicationData.category
});
var response = await post(
AppUrl.applications,
form,
headers: {
'Accept': 'application/json',
'Authorization': 'Bearer ' + userToken,
},
);
}
}

```

```

if (response.statusCode == 200) {
var receivedApplication = response.body['data'];
return Application.fromJson(receivedApplication);
} else {
return null;
}
}
Future<Application> editApplication(
EditApplication editApplicationData) async {
final UserPreferences userPreferences = Get.put(UserPreferences());
userPreferences.getUser();
var userToken = userPreferences.user.value.token;
final form = FormData({
'title': editApplicationData.title,
'description': editApplicationData.description,
'image_url':
MultipartFile(editApplicationData.imageUrl, filename: 'update.jpg'),50
'target_amount': editApplicationData.targetAmount,
'category_id': editApplicationData.category
});
var response = await post(
AppUrl.applications + '/${editApplicationData.id}',
form,
headers: {
'Accept': 'application/json',
'Authorization': 'Bearer ' + userToken,
},
);
if (response.statusCode == 200) {
var receivedApplication = response.body['data'];
return Application.fromJson(receivedApplication);
} else {
return null;
}
}
static Future<bool> deleteApplication(int applicationId) async {
final UserPreferences userPreferences = Get.put(UserPreferences());
userPreferences.getUser();
var userToken = userPreferences.user.value.token;
var response = await client.delete(
AppUrl.applications + "/$applicationId",
headers: {
'Accept': 'application/json',
'Authorization': 'Bearer ' + userToken,
},
);
if (response.statusCode == 200) {
return true;
} else {
return false;
}
}
}

```

}

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